

Underwater Data Logger Development: Bluetooth Wireless Communication Implementation for Monitoring

(Pembangunan Pengellog Data Bawah Air: Pelaksanaan Komunikasi Tanpa Wayar Bluetooth untuk Pemantauan)

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ABSTRACT

In the past five years of study in building an underwater data logger, researchers involved a microcontroller-based with sensors and a microSD card. But the main limitations are showing that the recorded parameters are limited while other case, the system diving can only go at most 30 meter and the other case is there is no mentioning on how the recorded file in microSD is required during reading process. Therefore, other alternatives are studied in this study which focuses on its use in underwater environment with maximum depth of 50m with multi-parameter. Wireless communication technique is presented which require recorded file of the parameters in the microSD through Bluetooth on a Bluetooth module HM-10 and a terminal of PuTTY. The main pillar of this system is the Arduino Uno microcontroller along with other sensors such as depth or pressure sensor with built-in temperature sensing called MS5803, salinity sensor TDS SKU: SEN0244, ambient light sensor TEMT6000 and GPS module U-Blox 6M. Robust underwater housings are constructed for this logger using PETG, Cylindrical Acrylic Tube, silicone-based O-Ring and an epoxy This combination turns this logger into a multi-level menu for the users. This paper describes a wide range of parameters to be recorded by a logger in underwater at most 50 meters.

Keywords: underwater data logger; environmental monitoring; PuTTY; Arduino-based logging platform; harsh environment

ABSTRAK

Pada lima tahun yang lalu bagi kajian dalam membina pengellog data bawah laut, para penyelidik melibatkan mikrokontroler dengan sensor dan kad microSD. Tetapi batasan utama adalah bahawa parameter yang dirakam adalah terhad sementara kes lain, sistem menyelam hanya dapat mencapai paling banyak 30 meter dan kes lain adalah tidak ada menyebut tentang bagaimana fail yang direkam dalam microSD diperlukan semasa proses membaca. Oleh itu, alternatif lain dikaji dalam kajian ini yang memfokuskan penggunaannya di persekitaran bawah laut dengan kedalaman maksimum 50m dengan multi-parameter. Teknik komunikasi tanpa wayar disajikan yang memerlukan fail parameter yang direkodkan dalam microSD melalui Bluetooth pada modul Bluetooth HM-10 dan terminal PuTTY. Tiang utama sistem ini adalah mikrokontroler Arduino Uno bersama dengan sensor lain seperti sensor kedalaman atau tekanan dengan sensor suhu terbina dalam yang disebut MS5803, sensor salinitas TDS SKU: SEN0244, sensor cahaya ambien TEMT6000 dan modul GPS U-Blox 6M. Perumahan bawah air yang kuat dibina untuk penebang kayu ini menggunakan PETG, Tiub Akrilik Silinder, O-Ring berasaskan silikon dan epoksi Kombinasi ini menjadikan pembalok ini menjadi menu pelbagai peringkat untuk pengguna. Makalah ini menerangkan pelbagai parameter yang akan direkodkan oleh penebang di bawah air paling banyak 50 meter.

Kata Kunci: pengellog data bawah air; pemantauan persekitaran; PuTTY; Pelantar pengellog berasaskan Arduino; persekitaran yang lasak

INTRODUCTION

The variation of underwater data logger either made by the industry or researchers are all had the same pattern of giving the basic needs of the definition of this type of logger. To be exact, those systems are included a microcontroller-based which the common is Arduino, with limited sensors which then the readings are recorded into a microSD and the whole system can go down only for 30 meters. The utmost reason of those limitations is because they want to keep a low cost and the investigation or objectives of the system is specific to record one or two underwater parameters which the common are temperature, salinity, and depth. A study conducted by Grant et. al. (2016), Arduino platform was chosen over Raspberry Pi and Gumstix because of its lower price and extensive online support network. Meanwhile, Theodore et. al. (2020), were only used a MS5803 to measure wave characteristics with the open-source Arduino software development environment.

When came to a data logger, it means there are two main processes which are recording and reading the data. Data here may include all the required parameters in the environment whether it is in the air or in the water while in this paper, the subject is in the water or to be specific it is in the tropical sea. Before, it has been stated how the limitations during recording process was seen

Knowledge Gap

Most used material in designing the enclosure of the system is Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC) because of its ability to be waterproof and resist to chemicals. But it degrades when exposed to Ultraviolet (UV). Till today, researchers for the underwater environment choose to implement this material in their project. Standard PVC pipe is used in the main waterproof housing by Grant et. al. (2016) to develop an Arduino-based Sonde for coastal applications at 4-meter subsurface depths. Meanwhile, the standard PVC is referring to ASTM D1785 which is the Standard Specification for PVC Plastic Pipe that specifically for water distribution and irrigation system.

The cons introduced by the PVC is indeed noted by the researchers and hence some has taken step to do mitigations on that. Patricia et. al. in their *Cave Pearl Data Logger* (2018), a protective coating of water based exterior latex has been used for the UV exposures while to reduce thermal stress on the electronic components. First to know that

throughout the previous studies where the number of parameters involvement is limited with low consideration of the length of depth that system can go down in water. Hence, the topic to be discussed later is about the methodology to cover the deficiency by introducing strong and waterproof housing and the involvement of variety of sensors. Now, as for the reading process, there is no findings on previous study about the technique to acquire the microSD card from the housing. Since the system is operating in the water environment, it is supposed to be a closed housing with an airtight and watertight capabilities. Instrument use in an underwater camera-TV system (Zhang et. al, 1987) has used a watertight underwater cubicle while it only needs to penetrate the seabed to about 100-150 mm. So, when the microSD card is needed, it is assumed that the closed housing is being opened. The mechanical design of the system housing can include one specific back door for the microSD card which is the same as the GoPro HERO9. It is important to know that it is not good for an airtight and watertight housing to be opened frequently as it will degrades the performance of that water and airtight capabilities over time. As being known in industry that watertight enclosures does not necessarily guarantee long-lasting protection and reliable performance because pressure differentials, which over time can cause leak paths.

latex paints consist of a pigment and binder with water used as a carrier (Kelly, 2019). Water based paint was initially introduced in 1865 when the first patent received by D. P. Flinn. Meanwhile, with the introduction of latex in 1940, the paint industry has been revolutionized and what to be noted here is that the purpose of its early use is its low cost due to a lower ratio of acrylic polymers. But, at the end of the day, the existence of the probability of the paint to not stick to all surfaces will expose the system enclosure to the UV and hence harm the inside electronic components.

Volatile memory has been used since 1984 by M. P. Pearson et. al. which used a tape cassette to store the recorded value of the levels of oxygen, temperature, and underwater light. Till recent, the invention of the volatile memory has been substituted to a non-volatile memory which the common is SD card. In a microcontroller-based such as Arduino, an SD module is required while the size of the SD or microSD card can be within 4 MB till 128 MB. Many studies form a .txt file or .csv file for the recorded parameters stored in the card. But the technique used is not found or

explained when file inside is to be read. Meanwhile, in this paper, it is not focusing in the mechanical design on making back door or separate compartments for the SD card itself. Instead, the lens is going towards the technology of wireless communication during the reading process as it increases the efficiency of the system. In short, the file data is required from the card through a wireless communication and passing through a 'bridge' called terminal to go into a computer. This function will need one more wireless module that compatible to the Arduino.

METHODOLOGY

Data Calibration

Calibration is a comparison between known (standard) measurements and measurements using other instruments. Typically, the accuracy given by the standard needs to be ten times more accurate compared to the accuracy of the instrument being tested. This method is carried out at the first stage in the whole process of building the study system. Such a thing is to identify any uncertainty of the measurement of the past instrument, an analysis can be made whether the deficiency can be fixed because it is due to technical errors or faulty software or even the instrument itself does not have high enough accuracy. Thus, it can be decided on the possibility of switching to other better instruments. As in this study, initially the depth and pressure sensor were MS5540C, but after a testing on the operating limits of the readings given, it was decided to replace it with another sensor that named MS55803.

Referring to the figure below, calibration of the pressure parameters was made by placing the book on top of a balloon containing the MS5803 sensor. Book variations were then added to see the difference in reading output by the sensor. The relation is then made by doing an analysis discussed in the later section. Instead of using a specialized temperature sensor for underwater use, DS18B20, MS5803 is also used to sense temperature as it has a temperature reading function. Further, calibration of the temperature parameter was carried out by contrasting it with the parameters given by the room thermometer. Whereas the variable used is room temperature and not water temperature. This is due to the lack of complete equipment and the pandemic situation that does not allow any meeting with the supervisor, to coat the sensor so that it is waterproof. So, it is possible to measure using room temperature because the difference is only in the density where it is generally known that the

density of water is higher than that of air which then causes the giving of the water temperature to be later than the air temperature. Hence, the water temperature should follow the air temperature or room temperature after a certain time. Another consequence of today's pandemic is that this depth sensor calibration from the same MS5803 cannot be accomplished and that is when an inference has been made in the end by using a relationship with the pressure value in an algorithm used in the programming.

FIGURE 1. Pressure sensor calibration

The TDS SKU: SEN 0244 salinity sensor consists of a probe, is an electric charge (EC) meter in which two electrodes (end probe needle) of equal distance are inserted into water and used to measure the charge. For this study, the sensor was calibrated with different amount of weighted salts. Then, analysis is made with the theoretical statement of the value of salt contained in the reality of the sea in the tropics to justify the ability of the sensor to work well in the targeted environment. Figure 2 explained the calibration for the light intensity sensor, TEMT 6000 which has been made in the comparison with smartphone application 'Lux Light Meter'. The application can measure the illumination of ambient conditions. Initially, the sensor was placed at the same distance as the smartphone that had the app. The first position between the two sensors with the light source from the voltage-powered lamp of three AAA-sized batteries is 50 cm. Lux unit light readings were then obtained and recorded. The position distance of the light source is subsequently varied according to a downward trend.

FIGURE 2. TEMT 6000 calibration

The Global Positioning System or GPS is a system for determining the exact geographical

location by the user. In the context of this study, a GPS module namely U-Blox Neo-6M was used to provide and store the location of the system before entering the waters. Then, the calibration of this module is easier because the comparison is only with the location standard given in Google maps that use Landsat 8 satellites.

Bluetooth communication testing

The second phase, development of Bluetooth communication carried out the process of reading data files in the microSD card which parted into two main parts. The first part is about selecting the right Bluetooth module to work in the Arduino Uno platform. Between three Arduino-compatible Bluetooth module; HC-05, HC-06 and HM-10, current consumption, Bluetooth version and sleep mode function are the elements of their differentiation. Then, the chosen module is tested for its performance on the functions required by the system.

Case Study for Multi-Level Menu Construction

A case study was made on the similarity of the case with the construction of the interface menu in this study system. It has involved a case in building a fast-food automated ordering system. Each fast-food menu has a defined price value of each of them. Thus, directly the method has eliminated the use of switch-case techniques in the programming languages involved in the early stages.

Experiment Design and Procedure

The design of the system in this paper is begin with the design of the electronic components. Referring to the Figure 3 below is the connection of all the components with the Arduino that makes one complete system. Firstly, when the system is powered on, the state is waiting for the user input to choose what process to execute either it is reading or recording process. In the meantime, of either one process is executed, the Real Time Clock (RTC) that use DS3231 model is working on in the background which during the recording of the parameter, the time is stamped on the file data. To remind the Bluetooth communication earlier, it is involved during the reading process, and this is where the system is already outside the water environment and there is a connected computer to receive the file data.

FIGURE 3. System Overview

As for the second design, it is about the mechanical design originated from a drawing on the OnShape platform. The three main materials used in Figure 4 (a) are Polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG) for all design columns, Acrylic Cylindrical Tube for the housing wall, and Silicone O-Ring as a liquid or gas ingress barrier. As such, PETG is a thermoplastic polyester that provides chemical resistance, durability, and its excellent capabilities for manufacturing. To further focus on the use of the material in this study, it has been compared with Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) because of its properties which are also very similar to each other. Thus, the comparisons made are based on durability, temperature resistance, Ultraviolet (UV) radiation resistance, price, and availability, and hygroscopic. Starting with durability, PETG has overtaken ABS due to the stronger PETG adhesion condition compared to ABS which has strong and poor coating adhesion. Therefore, PETG is capable of withstanding underwater as far as high depths and high pressures, as the target is 50 m. As for temperature resistance, ABS can withstand as high as 100 °C while PETG is lower at 80 °C. However, with such a small margin, PETG is more suitable and widely used in electronic applications which coincides with the joint study design of heat - emitting electronic components.

FIGURE 4. System's Mechanical Design
(a) OnShape 3D Design, (b) Bottom view of OnShape 3D Design

Further, PETG is in better condition under UV radiation due to the minimal radiation effect on it compared to ABS. Although the system will be in waters, it should be noted that UV radiation still also enters waters as far as 1000 meter. In addition, the cost of ABS is lower than PETG in addition to the availability of both in the market due to high demand rate. A good comparison for PETG despite having its higher hygroscopic deficiencies thus making it easier to absorb air humidity for example, water. It has automatically eliminated the excess of PETG as a material that will paste or set up system components. However, that statement has been limited by creating a system housing body wall from a cylindrical acrylic material. Two things that need to be discussed are the selection of the wall material and the shape of the cylinder. As defined, acrylic is a transparent plastic material with outstanding strength, stiffness, and exceptional optical clarity. The strength and stiffness required is to overcome the hygroscopic deficiencies of PETG that have been mentioned. scientifically and technically, acrylic will not cause curvature, bulging or loss of clarity with prolonged exposure to moisture or total immersion, as was also used in World War II as a seabed periscope. Thus, it has been proven that there is absolutely no entry of water or air through the acrylic wall with His permission. Furthermore, as is generally known that most marine life is cylindrical in shape if viewed roughly. No less so for submarines and other diving equipment that also have a cylindrical shape in general. The same has also been exemplified and practiced into the design of this study system because high seawater depth has implied hydratic-static pressure on the object and the seawater pressure encountered becomes constant from all directions even from the bottom. Thus, the clear purpose of the design of the cylinder shape is to distribute the water load uniformly to enclose the situation of deep-sea water as stated.

In the meantime, the O-Ring is known as a circular cross section designed to be installed in a groove and compressed during installation between two or more parts thus sealing between the two faces. cylinder. The O-Ring used in this context is made of silicone material due to its high resistance to high temperatures, high resistance to hot air and UV radiation, elastic, finer surface as a sealer than rubber material, as well as good resistance to corrosion. Referring to Figure 4 (b), it is the bottom and legs of the system housing. Since the salinity sensor probe rope is involved in this part where the probe needle needs to touch the water area to get a reading, then a water ingress barrier is required which is referred to as a cavity. The cavity used is from epoxy resin material due to its waterproof nature to chemicals, high sealing, its resistance to low temperature environment, as well as good electrical reliability. In addition, for tidiness and safety factors, the sensor probe strap is pinned to the foot of the figure.

Experiment Analysis

The calibration of each sensor has produced the expected data. which is used to provide correction of the measured data as well as perform uncertainty calculations on the sensor. Therefore, the sensors work accurately and free from any faults hence is enable for a good process control. The sensors that have been clarified are as follows:

1. MS5803
2. TDS SKU: SEN0244
3. TEMT6000
4. Blox Neo 6M

The level of depth under water is in line with the increase in pressure. Referring to the method of the calibration, relationship between the increasing pressure readings by the MS5803 sensor and the number of books placed on the balloon containing the sensor, has shown a linear feature. Generally, the weight of an object is a force caused by gravity and it can be replaced in the pressure equation. Thus, like the algorithm below, the pressure (P) caused by the weight (W) of an object is also the weight divided by the area (A) over which the weight is applied.

$$P = W/A \quad (1)$$

According to the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), at sea level, each square inch of surface will be subjected to a force of 14.6 pounds while the pressure will increase around one atmosphere (atm) for every 10

meters of water depth. Therefore, scientifically, at a depth of 50 meters of dive system of this study, the pressure reading by the sensor starting at sea surface will increase by 5 atm (5066.25 mbar). In addition, for the MS5803 sensor, the pressure reading limit that can be taken is 1400 mbar compared to the pressure sensor used previously which is only 1100 mbar. Basically, the sensor is not only capable of reading pressure parameters but also depth and temperature. However, the calibration of the depth function of the sensor could not be carried out due to the unfavorable pandemic conditions. Even so, an initial inference can be made for such depths that the higher the water depth, the higher the sea level reading read by the sensor. Thus, it has been concluded that these sensors can operate well under the ocean as far as the targeted dive.

The temperature function by MS5803 has been utilized. There is difference in temperature readings given by the sensor as well as from the physical sensor measuring room temperature. With reference to the purpose or existence of this data logger system under water, the temperature measured should be the water temperature. However, due to the lack of cavity material that needs to be placed on the sensor, the calibration of this data is based on room temperature only. The cavity material mentioned is due to the condition of the sensor, which is not waterproof, therefore the sensor board needs to be covered with epoxy or nail polish. Furthermore, the temperature difference

between the two sensors as in Figure is approximately 1.66 °C.

The salinity of seawater that can be measured by TDS SKU: SEN0244 which has been calibrated. Starting with the absence of salt (Figure 5), the value of TDS was observed which is approximately 0 ppm (parts per million). The readings taken were in line with the increase in salt content so that at 45 ml of salt, the TDS value was 1236 ppm. Similarly, the TDS value at 50 ml remained at 1236 ppm. Both conditions are because the sensor capability is a maximum of 1200 ppm only as in the data sheet. Thus, it can be concluded that no matter how much the salinity content of the water, the TDS value is static at approximately 1200 ppm.

The average salinity of seawater as stated by NOAA, it is around 35 parts per thousand or parts per thousand (ppt) which is 3.5% by weight of seawater derived from dissolved salt. Meanwhile, for the target waters of this study system which is a tropical ocean in the Indian Ocean has a total area of 68,556 million km² and the surface salinity of the waters ranged between 32 to 37 ppt. As a rule, it is necessary to know that the water surface of an ocean has stretched as deep as 100 meters below. Theoretically, for the calibrated 1200 ppm saltwater salinity limit, it shows a reading of 1.2 ppt sea salinity which is 3.5% of the median average salinity of the Indian Ocean. Therefore, it can be concluded that as far as a depth as high as 100 meters, this study system is capable of reading water salinity as high as 3.5% only.

FIGURE 5. Salinity Calibration Data
TDS SKU: SEN 0244

The ambient light focused on this data logger system is that generated by sunlight and does not include artificial light from a strobe or user video light underwater. Thus, the value level of the parameter is measured by TEMT6000. Looking at

Figure 6, the ambient value given by the sensor is in line with the LUX application sensor. Only when the distance between the light source and the two sensors is 22 cm, the ambient value by the application sensor is 120 lux while for the system

sensor is lower which is 100 lux. Thus, an initial conclusion can be made that the higher the distance between the light source and the sensor, the lower

the value of ambient light intensity will be measured.

FIGURE 6. Ambient Light Calibration Data TEMT 6000

Determining the location of the system before entering the water is by using U-Blox Neo 6M. Therefore, it does not need to work when in the water, so the calibration carried out is like the figure below where the latitude and longitude values of the selected location are proportional to the location on Google Map.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Constructed Bluetooth Communication

Among the Bluetooth components as mentioned in the study methods chapter, the HM-10 was selected to function in this study system. This is because of its specifications that meet the required characteristics such as sleep mode function, low current consumption, and low energy consumption. The sleep mode function is required when the user chooses to record data instead of reading data on the microSD card. Therefore, if the user chooses to read the data on the microSD, the sleep mode will be disabled and then, the reading of the data occurs by communicating with the computer via Bluetooth communication. As illustrated in Figure 7, the data read is in the form of .txt which can also be included in Microsoft Excel as .csv. The read data is then automatically stored in the computer via the PuTTY terminal.

3D Printed Mechanical Design

Figure 8 shows the 3D printed of the whole system enclosure to go for at most 50 meter in the water. The assembly of the electronic components in Figure 3 with Figure 8 has not able to be accomplished. This is due to the complex situation of current pandemic of Covid-19. The remaining observation to be made is the performance of the expected system to stand in the high pressure for at most 5066.25 mbar in the 50 meter in the sea water.

FIGURE 8. 3D printed system enclosure

20210111_160033 - Notepad

File Edit Format View Help

-----PuTTY log 2021.01.11 16:00:33-----

y 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:48	26.9 °C	6 ppm	10 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:49	26.9 °C	6 ppm	11 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:50	26.9 °C	6 ppm	8 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:51	26.9 °C	6 ppm	10 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:52	26.9 °C	6 ppm	10 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:54	26.9 °C	6 ppm	11 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:55	26.9 °C	6 ppm	8 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:56	26.9 °C	6 ppm	12 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:57	26.9 °C	6 ppm	11 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:58	26.9 °C	6 ppm	8 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:24:59	26.9 °C	6 ppm	10 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:25:00	26.9 °C	6 ppm	11 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:25:01	26.9 °C	6 ppm	11 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:25:02	26.9 °C	6 ppm	10 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:25:03	26.9 °C	4 ppm	11 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:25:04	26.9 °C	4 ppm	11 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:25:05	26.9 °C	4 ppm	10 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 11:25:06	26.9 °C	4 ppm	10 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:27	26.9 °C	0 ppm	16 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:28	26.6 °C	0 ppm	15 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:29	26.9 °C	0 ppm	8 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:30	26.9 °C	0 ppm	8 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:31	26.6 °C	0 ppm	17 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:32	26.9 °C	0 ppm	8 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:34	26.9 °C	0 ppm	16 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:35	26.9 °C	0 ppm	16 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:36	26.9 °C	0 ppm	8 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:37	26.9 °C	0 ppm	16 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:38	26.9 °C	0 ppm	16 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:39	26.9 °C	0 ppm	8 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:40	26.9 °C	0 ppm	16 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:41	26.9 °C	0 ppm	8 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:42	26.9 °C	0 ppm	8 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:43	26.9 °C	0 ppm	16 lux
Monday 04.01.2021 -- 12:01:44	26.9 °C	0 ppm	8 lux

FIGURE 7. Stored .txt file in microSD card

Figure 9 gives a clear picture of the overall flow chart of the system. Starting with the user interface, there are two main options that will be selected via a rotary encoder button that then leads to the process of recording or reading data. When the recording process is selected, the RTC or real-time clock starts while the Bluetooth module enters sleep mode. After that, all the sensors involved start reading the parameters in the waters, the readings are recorded and stored in a file that has been set on the microSD card that has been opened. Each entry made in the selected time interval on the file, the file will be closed and then repeat the process of opening the file until the time has been reached then the process ends.

Further, when the process of reading the data selected by the user, a Bluetooth module is developed and waits for connection with a computer. After the connection, the Bluetooth module reads the data file in the microSD card that has been opened and then displays the reading on the computer through a terminal called PuTTY. Then, the completed reading display is then automatically saved into a computer file in .txt format.

FIGURE 9. System Programming

CONCLUSION

There are elements that give ideas for further improvement for example on the components' limitations of the system with the user interface. Hence, the thing to be emphasized in this context is based on two main things, namely from the point of view of physical and system software.

As for its physical point of view, further comment could not be well identified due to the test not being conducted but based on the initial hypothesis, it is suggested that. Whereas, in terms of software, it refers to the physical capabilities mentioned by which the system needs to interact with the user about the data collected at anytime and anywhere. The main areas of the proposed improvement to this underwater data logging system are real - time monitoring during data logging as well as the alternative use of salinity sensors.

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